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Digital Network Marketing and its Postcolonial Discourses in the Political Economy of Reading: Exploring ‘Literary’ Sites in Cyberspace Cultural Studies

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Abstract

This paper set out to rethink digital networking as a strategic discourse from which to expand the prospects of a critical model of cultural studies in ICT marketing consultancy. Drawing insights from critical theory and starting from the premise that the digital network strategy is not inclusive enough of businesses, communities and individuals, as it ought to be, the paper proposes a new ‘literary’ and cultural model that incorporates the media of the commons, political engagement, upliftment of societal standards of living, brand culture and language appropriation. It illustrates this critical ‘literary’ and cultural model by drawing from network platforms like LinkedIn, Myspace, Facebook, Youtube Twitter, blogging, Google+, Instagram, Pinterest, Podcasting, Snapchat Tumblr, Blog spot, and Wordpress. In order to re-embed the postcolonial ‘literary’ context in digital networking and show the perspectives of the network platform as a potentially emancipative metanarrative, it takes inspiration from case examples of studies of democracy in the Arab spring, electoral politics in African countries like Zimbabwe and Kenya, the Mexican food chain Chipotle, the film industry and companies like Apple.

Keywords: *Digital network strategy, sites of literary discourse, crowdculture branding, ICT cultural studies, media of the commons, language appropriation, postcolonial ‘writings’*

1.0 Introduction

This paper rethinks digital network marketing as a strategic discourse for a new literary model with a view to show how its long term effectivity is ultimately contingent upon its critical context, namely, the critical narratives of content in the political economy. It suggests how an integrative approach to the political economy context can be critical to the ROI of digital companies depending on networking in the contemporary age of the knowledge economy. The paper aims to delineate such areas of digital networking and rich content identifying possible intervention measures for a literary model. Although businesses are deploying media networking to promote their market share, scholarship on its literary *usability* in the context of the larger political economy of content is still scant (Artha, Hernández-García and Lamberti, 2013). As a result, companies use social media marketing strategies like networking guided more by trial, error and intuition or by rationalization principles than by critical literary assessment. This paper proposes an integrated framework of rich content that identifies possible actionable contexts aligned to digital strategies of networking. Such a critical context can support marketing performance and productivity for businesses and organizations and therefore open up perspectives for exploring a literary model of ICT marketing. The subsequent sections consider the limits to dependency on networking alone as a strategy to achieve high digital market productivity, discuss why marketing productivity is low in this regard, and conclude with recommendations of this critical literary model of ICT marketing to improve overall marketing performance via critical networking strategies in the future.

In the light of these preoccupations, the paper attempts to answer a series of questions that intersect digital marketing networks and conversion from casual purchasers as ‘literary readers’ to brand ambassadors in order to leverage a healthy and sustainable competitive advantage. For example, how should we enforce digital advertisements in creative and literary ways? What is the role of networks of information in today’s society of the capital, democracy, and power and how can we induce a more productive society of digital networks by drawing from literary resources? More specifically, we shall find out how political struggles emerge from social media networks, which contemporaneous cultural developments are linked to the digital networks of marketing and how these developments instruct us about the potentialities of digital marketing networks as a strategy for the future. It raises these issues in terms of how to render the internet itself more efficient and responsive to societal changes and needs, thereby constructing a digitally oriented commons-based and participatory

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democracy ethics that leverages co-operation and sustainability from literary resources. There is no doubt that we have now entered a new imperial age of the ICT knowledge economy; we are now entrenched in what is referred to variously as the age of informational capitalism, finance capitalism, hyper-industrial capitalism, crisis capitalism (Fuchs 2012). But in this age of the digital knowledge economy, social media networking alone is not effective because digital networking is not deployed in a technological vacuum; it is (re-)constructed by the 'literary' environment where nations and states function as 'reading' consumers. Thus, beyond networks of blogs (e.g. Blogspot, Wordpress), social networking sites (e.g. Facebook), microblogs (e.g. Facebook, LinkedIn, Weibo), wikis (e.g. Wikipedia, WikiLeaks), user-generated content and file sharing sites (e.g. YouTube, the Pirate Bay), there is the literary context of contemporary capitalist culture with its own participatory, democratic and creative ethics, and the reality of precarity, exploitation, inequalities and power asymmetries. It is this literary environment of audiences, constituting a collective intelligence that is even re-creating the value assigned to network platforms such as Facebook. Wikipedia, Amazon, Google or Craigslist in what has been termed as a "community of connected users" (O'Reilly and Battelle 2009).

2.0 Methodological framework

The methodological framework of this paper draws insights from Jeremy Weate's post-colonial social narratives as public 'writings' (Weate 2003, 2003), the 'literary actions' employed to sustain relationship and transactional marketing as suggested by Artha Sejati Ananda, Ángel Hernández-García and Lucio Lamberti (2013) and Rob Cover (2013) and from Christian Fuch's (2017) Marxist-oriented paradigms about the literary commons. It re-positions digital marketing network in the artistic context of critical (social) theory, so as to offer insights on optimization of customer-focused 'readership' of signifiers as opposed to strictly digital marketing. Rob Cover's (2013) *Online Identities: Creating and Communicating the Online Self* enquires into the ways in which identity representations are shifting ever since the advent of ICTs. For over a hundred years, critical studies have shown that identity is multifaceted; everyday people develop a changing sense of themselves, their attitudes, desires, representations and behaviours. In this age of digital, networked interactivity, the identity of states and nations is becoming more complex as digital users are playing a greater and extensive role in moulding their own online self-representations, and are co-creating group and common metanarratives of identity via user-generated and audio-visual online content. Digital media has complexified the 'literary' culture of identity through social, world-wide, inter-cultural networking and interactive sites. The paper draws inspiration from Christian Fuch's (2017) critical framework in *Social Media: A Critical Introduction*, for understanding social media platforms in contexts of media power, political economy, participation, the literary culture of the commons, democracy and public collaboration, surveillance and privacy and political ethics.

The digital universe deeply moulds how people consume, work, create, socialize, and play. People are very enmeshed in digital networks (e.g. social media, cell phones, etc), to such a point where it is difficult to imagine an 'outside' or an alternative to the logic and power of Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Pinterest and so forth. Yet, there is an 'outside' to the digital network that Ulises Ali Mejias' (2013) work entitled *Off the Network:: Disrupting the Digital World*, rethinks and questions. The critical insights it offers interrogates the ascendancy of the network strategy touted as inclusive, consensual, although we have reservations as far as aspects like monopolization and commodification are concerned. The 'literary' network broadens social participation but at the same time exacerbates disparity and excludes the greater part of society than it incorporates. Therefore, the challenge that this paper address is how to review corporate spaces such as Twitter and Facebook from both 'within and outside' the network discourse so that they should be more inclusive for ordinary businesses, communities and individuals all over the 'reading' cultural world.

3.0 Findings:

3.1 From digital networking to the social context of social media

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The strategy of networking intersects with ‘social media’ which has now split up into multiple *signifiers*, such as corporate media, ‘participatory media,’ ‘media-industries’, and its content has even opened up into multiples of contexts such as ‘user-generated content’, ‘convergence culture’, ‘audience’, ‘peer-production’ and ‘Web 2.0’ (Mandiberg 2012: 2). But the media network is now entangled with the challenge of how to identify new economic contexts of internet businesses in the aftermath of the “dot.com” crisis, the bursting of financial bubbles and the advent of the “web 2.0”. Today, the new discourse is about the second emergence of the Web after the dotcom bust.” The new challenge is how to restore confidence in this industry that has “...lost its way” (O’Reilly and Battelle 2009, 1). Web 2.0 needs to seduce venture capital investments for new internet businesses. It is capitalist in terms of relations of production but also informational and literary at the level of forces of production. Production is carried out for the sake of profit and with the employment of knowledge and information technology. The orthodoxy in digital marketing scholarship is that digital networks enable individuals, companies, organizations, startups, etc to construct a public profile in an (in-out) bounded system; to enlist their users with whom they can share connections and view and traverse their listings of connections as well as connections created by other users in the system (Ellison and Boyd 2007, Agwu and Murray 2013).

Digitized marketing networks are not deployed in a vacuum, but are applied in a very fluid and literary context characterized by economic, political, social, cultural and other forms of dynamics. As the driving engine of the world’s contemporary political economy, we need to investigate digital media networks in their cultural and literary context, that is, in relationship to their interaction with the emerging capitalist society and generally the power structures that regulate social stratification, gender, class, race, etc. Social media marketing is a recent phenomenon that began with social media dominating online communication. Social media marketing is a form of internet marketing that implements various social media networks in order to achieve marketing communication and branding goals. Social media marketing primarily covers activities involving social sharing of content, videos, and images for marketing purposes. Social media marketing programmes usually center on efforts to create content that attracts attention and encourages ‘readers’ to share it with their social networks, resulting in electronic word of mouth strategies. When the underlying message spreads from audience to audience and presumably resonates because it appears to come from a trusted, third-party source, as opposed to the brand or company itself, this form of marketing is socially grounded. Marketing techniques adopted by social media marketing include targeting, consumers’ online brand related activities, electronic word of mouth, and so on, and these techniques are used for advertising online successfully. Social media networks such as Facebook and Twitter provide advertisers with information about the ‘likes’ and ‘dislikes’ of their consumers which is crucial, as it provides the businesses with a *target audience*. Consumer’s online brand related activities are used by advertisers to promote their products. An activity such as uploading the picture of a product purchased on Facebook is an example of a consumers’ online brand related activities. In the electronic word of mouth method, electronic recommendations and appraisals are a convenient manner to have a product promoted via user-to-user interactions. An example would be a review of a company online. A good service would result in a positive review that gets the company free advertising via social media; however, a poor service may issue from a negative consumer review which can potentially ruin the company’s reputation of marketing results in earned media rather than paid media. Online marketing, which is also referred to as internet marketing, is the process of promoting a brand, service or product on the internet by combining the technical and creative or cultural aspects of the World Wide Web; it includes website development, blog marketing, email marketing and article marketing. Social media marketing and online marketing are often used interchangeably; however, there are subtle differences. Social media marketing is a component of online marketing, which has become a useful tool for entrepreneurs or small business owners as well as corporations. Whereas social media marketing is conducted through social networks i.e., Facebook, Twitter, etc; social media marketing helps in creating business and consumer relationships through interaction with other members of these social networks. YouTube is popular for video marketing, which is also considered as part of social media marketing since it is becoming a social and cultural networking site. YouTube is an excellent tool to market one’s products and services to one’s target audience. So, how can digital marketing strategies be deployed as a driving engine of the political

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economy of the world to align with the powerful forces of social and cultural change? Can we measure social and cultural change and particularly the direction it is taking to know if the direction is ambiguous, that is, prone to literary interpretation either positively or negatively? How can we manage this dialecticism of signs in such a way that outcomes truly emancipate businesses irrespective of the direction of cultural change rather than watch social change cast a spell of disaster on humanity? How can we render more efficient digital marketing networks as strategic tools for organizational marketing management to promote their products and services?

3.2 From determinism of digital media network to market culture of content

The digital networking strategy draws from the ‘social’ and literary culture in very rich ways. The term ‘social media’ derives from ‘social’ and ‘media’. Media comes from ‘medium’, which signifies a channel, or a platform where user-generated content is created and exchanged. The social channels of networking include LinkedIn, Myspace, Facebook, Youtube Twitter, blogging, Google+, Instagram, Pinterest, Podcasting and Snapchat. The word ‘social’ in ‘social media’ is used in the sense of interactivity among individuals, people, groups and communities, who show a common interest in the progress of their societies. There are now over a billion users all over the world using these media networks through sites where people socialize, create relationships, build friendships, and interact among themselves (Vanessa 2012). Various races of people share interests, construct activities, expose backgrounds and set up connections. But beyond network interactions is the instilling of loyalty feelings, answering of questions (Assaad 2011), discovery, reading and sharing of news, information and knowledge and so forth. As a result, online network audiences are empowered to express themselves culturally through information exchange, distribution of comments, reviews of products, services and brands and so on. These media platforms and networks have been appropriated not only by the military, but especially by business managers and marketers (Bacon 2011) to promote products, brands and services to customers, and in this way, they reach them easily and cheaply by simply clicking a digital button. The technologies are highly scalable and accessible with the potential to increase exposure and traffic (Stelzner 2013). The commodification of all products, services, brands, etc, resulted in the commodification of the communication commons, and by this very dialectic, internet communication was commercialized as the driving engine of the political economy of customer ‘readership’. The old oral method of word of mouth that was used in traditional societies in Africa and in indigenous human civilizations as a marketing strategy, is now being refined into the electronic word of mouth and is further reshaped into what is now referred to as programmes for consumer’s online brand related activities. Because growth of the forces of information production is itself contradictory and expansion comes in conflict with capitalist relations of production, new phenomena have emerged in the market arena such as file sharing on the internet, the debate on intellectual property rights, the advent of pirate parties in the political backdrop of western countries, and the popularity of free software (Fuchs 2008).

Beyond the marketer’s deployment of network tools for publicity, to increase visibility and promote products and services, update information about products, services, events, index business sites through search engines etc (Kietzmann 2013), there is the online engagement of audiences in the exchange of ideas and knowledge, thereby addressing local solutions to problems, constructing trust among consumers of a given peer group through comments on Facebook, re-tweeting on Twitter about a specific organization, product, service or organization (Assaad and Gómez 2011). The quality of communication has increased: it is constant, just-in-time, and optionable (Kietzmann 2013, Southern 2013). The technology has increased exposure for businesses, traffic for startups, and the presence of entrepreneurship on Facebook, Twitter, Tumblr, LinkedIn, Instagram, Google+ and Pinterest. There are now 1.415 billion users on Facebook, 288 million users on Twitter, but what is worrying is that *most of the presence* of corporations, organizations, businesses and individuals online are not focused, do not have strategies, nor do they have any intention to commit to the digital market (Agwu and Carter 2013). They do not master content, which is the backbone of digital media (Bacon 2011); they do not commit to any online audience to improve sales, patronage, goodwill, brand affiliation, loyalty and promote/defend product, service, cause, etc; they do not hone their skills of graphics, research, designs, backend

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management, analytics, optimization, monitoring, etc. and they are not consistent or regular (Bennett 2013). Consequently, most online presence does not promote loyal fans (Colliander and Dahlén 2011), does not improve sales (Drury 2008), increase their exposure (Dean A (2013), grow partnerships with other businesses, generate leads, reduce market expenditure (Richard 2009), improve their search rankings, increase traffic to their sites, nor possess any marketplace insight (Kietzmann JC (2013)

As a direct or indirect result of these digital network realities, certain negative/positive effects are now observable in social media marketing, namely, the shift of critical power from the market producer to the consumer. The consumer is now in a position to articulate their preoccupations negatively or positively to millions of other customers, and this has engendered the epoch of the *online consumer*, who is now the driving force of these businesses, startups, organizations, etc. As a consequence of these lapses, e-marketers have to rethink how to get in touch and ‘converse’ with consumers (Kietzmann 2013), how to process the new signifiers of unpredictability and uncontrollability, over speech act and thought. Digital power has shifted over to the digital consumer, who has appropriated interactivity with other consumers, is constructing relations with individuals, is free to interact with companies, to personalize his connectivity with organizations and in these ways, is challenging the old methods of advertising and outbound marketing (Assaad and Gómez 2011). As a consequence of this *power shift* empowering the consumer to choose whom to follow online, the products, services and brands of e-marketers are increasingly reaching constricted target audiences of consumers. This is a good outcome for consumers; however, it is bad news for the performance of organizations, their motivation, output, etc (Richard 2009, Abbey 2007). This transfer of power to the individual customer by social media has impacted not only on businesses, but also on the strategies of marketing themselves because the punch of ads or the issues of colour in striking images are not the end of the story; there is a transition to new questions like the need for incessant dialogue, construction of trust, interactivity with a niche audience, questions of the right way of communicating, temporality, etc.

Consumers are now connected and participate in the lives of other consumers by digitally observing and reading them. For example, with the Facebook option of clicking ‘likes’, a brand may go viral on various channels because consumers may feel relaxed with the opinions of their peers than with the paid ads of businesses, even if they are more informed (Kietzmann 2013). Companies are now making recourse to reviews of their products, brands and services via YouTube videos, which are distributed and shared and disseminated through other sites and these reviews assist consumers in making their purchase decisions. Company brands are given to YouTube users who are influencers to review for their own subscription clients. When it comes to negative reviews, the new thinking is that companies should not systematically go defensive or reject them outrightly; rather, they can leverage the dissatisfaction of consumers to change or ameliorate the brands, products or services they offer. They may request the opinions of customers about events that are scheduled to come concerning their brands (Agwu and Murray 2013). Social ‘bakers’ can enable companies and organizations to know what is trending through media analytics and data analytics for brands on Facebook, Twitter, Google+, LinkedIn, YouTube, Instagram, and VK (Carlson 2010). They can monitor and optimize their campaign efficiency and KPIs in order to improve their marketing success and efficiency. The site provides data on the fastest growing presence on social media according to industry i.e., celebrity, brands, entertainment, etc.

The impact of digital marketing networking on customers has had repercussions on digital models of marketing. Two models of marketing were advocated as a direct result of the transfer of power from corporations, businesses and organizations to the consumer. The so-called 4Cs often led to confusion because they highlighted different spheres of intervention. Lauterborn’s 4Cs provides that: consumers have wants and needs, need convenience to buy, have to communicate and have costs to satisfy. These 4Cs came to replace the 4Ps that constituted the old market mix (Lauterborn 1990). Bob Lauterborn explained that the 4Ps (as opposed to the 7Ps) were obsolete and had to be replaced to address the real questions of marketing in the era of the consumer. He suggested that the ‘consumer has wants and needs’ and so the concentration on products or services by businesses is outdated because the focus is now on things or issues that consumers do not need or want. Nokia company, for example, fabricated many products, but failed to satisfy their consumers’ wants and

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needs. The author's paradigm of 'cost to satisfy' assumes that price is irrelevant because the multiples of other factors are involved. This applies to commodity goods, like supermarket purchases, in which purchasers negotiate a price they pay with suppliers. A supplier may, in this case, provide a 'cost to satisfy' her purchasers. However, the challenge is with the terms 'cost to satisfy' when it comes to a corporation like Apple for whom the 'cost to satisfy' may be read more like an inferior price offer whereas products of Apple are premium-priced. For a brand such as Apple, the cost to satisfy has to be elevated than that for the competitors, in order to articulate the brand as a luxury product. An Apple iPad Air 2, for example, does not have a 'cost to satisfy' irrespective of the place because the price is the same worldwide. The Apple iPad Air 2 (i.e. the Space Grey Apple A8X, iOS 8, 9.7", Wi-Fi, 64GB,) cost £479.00 in UK shops because it was supervised by the Apple brand, to prevent discounting. When it comes to 'convenience to buy' the old paradigm of 'P' for 'Place' was weak because of contact with product alliterated with Place. In the digital world, convenience transcoded into a 24/7 availability time schedule and the idea of shopping became redundant. In the digital world, there is no such thing as break time at lunch hours, lateness, etc. Digital marketing ended disintermediation and promoted direct purchase, although UK insurance broker 'Compare the Market' amalgamated car insurance policies in a computer so that different policies can be contrasted by clients; Expedia reinvented re-intermediation by aggregating offers for holidays in a fixed place, and Skyscanner organized flights for particular dates in a given site. Lauterborn's communication discountenanced promotion as a controlling and calculative one-way paradigm and reinvented communications from the company to consumers as dialogue. Dialogue became a two-path conversation, with consumers developing user-generated content. In this template, the customer became the target market and indeed the king of all attention. He had access to all the details about companies.

Apple does not apply all aspects of the overall template. For example, it continues to depend on 'Physical evidence', which is one of the 7Ps, and a central consideration in its proposition. As its marketing mix, Apple products have to look and feel in particular ways which the 4Cs do not deal with. So, the template was found to be amenable with small businesses and less complex firms to deploy in B2B because of its narrow focus that does not take into account people, physical evidence and processes. Two decades later, this model was replaced by yet another model, namely, the 4Cs of marketing communications comprised of clarity, consistency, credibility and competitiveness (Jobber and Fahy 2009). Jobber and Fahy affirm that after identification of the target audience and segmentation of the marketing of a business, the next step has to be a positioning statement by the 4Cs as a way of constructing an online value proposition. In most B2B slogans, the criteria of Clarity, Consistency, Credibility are met safely for Competitiveness which cannot be easily communicated via luxury brands. A UK business like Sainsbury conveys competitiveness through the catchphrase: 'Live well for less.' The UK supermarket like Morrisons articulates the spirit of competitiveness through its watchword: 'Love it cheaper'

so, when the competitiveness spirit is expressed, Price becomes the predominant factor, together with performance in B2B companies dealing with products of technology. The spirit of competitiveness may also be appreciated through customer service standards. When developing a catchword for an online value proposition, some of the 4Cs may be left out but watchwords must have clarity and must be credible. Thus, digital marketing strategies are not a fixed narrative applied by companies and organizations but are marked by clear shifts from 7Ps to the first template of 4Cs and the second model of 4Cs.

As a direct or indirect result of the empowerment of the network consumer (Kunz and Hackworth 2011), digital marketing is coming under concentrated scrutiny and increasing censure from CEOs, consultancies, who question its value added to corporations and shareholders as opposed to costs. Consulting firms underline the marketing dysfunctions of networks to meet objectives (Sheth 2013). Consequently, corporations like P&G scaled back on coupons, decreased lines of production, discontinued brands, reduced distribution centres, and diverted ads to web pages in order to minimize market costs from 20% and from 25% of net sales (Ibid). AT&T outsourced its consumers to save \$500NI per year; IBM limited its ads agencies from sixty five to two all over the world; and Coca-Cola is disbursing 5650M to develop enterprise software and incorporate business

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processes internationally. In order to optimize sales, the corporation decided that adopt supply chain management and service and sales automation, in order to ameliorate market efficiency (Ibid). Consulting firms like Booz Allen & Hamilton in 1994, Coopers & Lybrand in 1993. and McKinsey in 1994 investigated performance in market productivity and found them to be decreasing. Webster (1980) found that thirty CEOs of major corporations were preoccupied with diminishing productivity and increasing market expenditure, low skills in financial connotations of market actions, and the absence of entrepreneurship and innovation. Market academics are worried about market performance, asset-based evaluation, value discounted cash flows and shareholder value creation, and sales and market share.

4.0 Discussion

4.1 From online market networking to popular political engagement

Social media networking (Twitter, Facebook, YouTube, etc.) has been constructed into different forms of political re-engagement, which is now the setting for actively expressed dissatisfaction with political elites resulting to uproars in nation states like Tunisia, Libya, Yemen, Bahrain, and Egypt (Wiest 2011). The most exploited websites, namely, Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, Tumblr, Blog spot, WordPress and LinkedIn are the most deployed platforms which concentrate on communication, collaboration, community consciousness-building and community-maintenance. The platforms stand in the context of power, exploitation, domination, oppression, class, digital labour, ideology, protest and struggles. The ICT has become a new narrative strategy for nations as ICTs have been able to narrate the nation (Bhabha 1994) in impactful ways because they also use visuals and audio techniques as open space for information and apathy. Nationals use smartphones, tablets, and social media like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn, Pinterest, Youtube and Whatsapp as their driving force for the narration of consciousness and nationalism. It has paved the way for groups with diverse political interests and social welfare agendas to articulate their preoccupations. The Arab spring in Tunisia was aided by social media. Folks rallied to join a demonstration campaign against the state through Twitter and Facebook.

Public information distributed via social networking plays an important role in politics and drives activism. A Facebook page on which politics in Zimbabwe is discussed is called *Baba Jukwa*. This Facebook site is controversial but has great influence over community politics. The internet serves as a laboratory of political experiments for reconfiguring the repertoires of political actions in African and other nation states (Dobra 2012). ICT serves as a democratic enhancer by capturing the African endogenous productions of political modernity. The biometric system of e-voting is now introduced in some African countries like Zimbabwe, Zambia, Somalia and Ghana (Muza 2013). ICTs are appropriating and indigenizing localizing instances of resistance like the exposed bodies of *Takembeng* grandmothers in Cameroon, which defies prescriptive Western paradigms and falls under the “African model of ICT practice”, the context of an African self-defined political reality. Therefore, ICTs are playing a major role in electoral politics in some nation states like Kenya, Liberia, Rwanda and Sierra Leone where the use of technology is deciding electoral outcome (Collings 2013). Even people with chronic health conditions have now formed digital constituencies of activism online (Gillett 2003).

4.2 From online market networking to social constituencies

From the viewpoint of investment in the social context, Apple is an example of a very successful brand (from \$8 billion in 2004 to \$180 billion in 2013), but this success is as a result of the fact that, beyond the strategy of networking through Google or Facebook PPC ads for its brand, namely, the iPhone, iPod, the iPad, etc, the company utilized its computer products and services to fulfill a social purpose and critical mission, namely, to render life easier, cool, more fun, and better, and this requirement raised new questions, not simply of products and modes of channeling, but especially of the utility and design purpose of products and services (Jenkins 1983, Benady 2013, Southern 2014). As a result, Apple invested in the placement of products in places where pop icons, superstars, and other celebrity icons met and in popular shows. The company invested in the

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construction of buzz via positive media reviews. In order to supplement networking, it offered a free trial programme in which its products/services were offered in exchange for a positive testimonial. In addition, the social approach requires that customers who are contented and satisfied with products and services should be contacted and asked for their positive testimonials and reviews. Such encouraging reviews and testimonials can be published on a site. They can be helpful in swaying conversion of consumers not only into clients but also into subscribers. This is a context where creativity counts a lot and there is no rigid one way of going about it. When a testimonial is posted, a picture or an *avatar* can be associated with it in such a way that there is a rich information flow: e.g. the contributor's names, address, interests, etc can be added to build digital realism and a link can be pasted back to the reviewer's own website. Now this context is important because social proof can also be critical to the consumer's positive review of a product/service or brand and social proof accords greater authenticity to a niche market.

In order to galvanize *the trust of* customers, consumers must see that a recommendation has been made by a friend, an indigenous relative, a family member, a gender/generational group, etc. Consumers generally trust the opinions, reviews, etc of other consumers *like* themselves which are posted online, especially if these posts show how a problem was raised, how it was analyzed, how solutions were arrived at and proposed, how they were applied and how the outcome was a happy one. This kind of methodology can generate leads, drive traffic and facilitate conversions. In order to augment market share, one can also associate with insiders of celebrity idols and influencers. In this case, an influencer has to be persuaded to perceive value in a product/service and she has to see that that value is relevant to the specific niche or audience the brand is intended for. From here, that value can be conveyed to consumers so as to share with them and also share with others who have the same interests. It is not enough to *commence a* network of PPC ad campaign; in order to optimize a PPC ad campaign, the platform must be chosen carefully. The landing page should be clean, scripted well, and a clear call-to-action should be made so that consumers do not get confused with what they have to do. In this light, the landing page and the ad copy should be thoroughly aligned in conformity with the interests of consumers.

Then, there is the vexing social question of price 'wars,' that is, the issue of determining the worthiness of a product/service through the price factor that society is ready to pay for. The concern with the social means that a company should go beyond mere preoccupations with the price and stress unique value propositions (UVPs) that society can benefit from. The orthodox belief in economism is that when prices are reduced, products/services will be competitive on the market and this would minimize customer attrition. But a networking strategy that focuses on such a narrow economic approach can have a negative result for a company, because a narrow focus on price wars can hurt a company's chances to compete. At least, Apple avoided this trap; it did not seek to underbid its prices in order to optimize market share. Rather, beyond its networking strategy and because it was prioritizing the larger societal interests of consumers, it adopted a methodology that consisted of betting on *quality* as opposed to gambling in networks on price. In this regard, the sociological suggested that what was important was *the consumer* and not the price: Apple did not compromise on questions that had to do with the quality of its brand: 'You get what you pay for', nor did it fall into concessions when it came to matters of providing data evidence, written content, research proof on the persuasive *quality* of its products/services on the consumer. Apple's UVP emphasized quality as the foundation stone of its marketing insights and a road picture aligned those insights with the social by incorporating the aesthetics of *design* for the enjoyment of consumers and the utility function of their brand for their overall satisfaction. As a result, consumers were more inclined to spend more in order to gain greater quality than to spend less in order to a loss in terms of lesser quality. So, while the question of 'price' was, of course, important in terms of 'profit', the priority for Apple was on the value that society gained from brand quality. Quality does not compete with anything, rather, it is simply perceived and consumed by society. The price of a product/service is just one perspective from which one can see it; there is a whole gamut of other features and specifications of a brand and 'quality' is the 'umbrella' that covers them. In addition to 'price', features and specifications of a brand have to do with brand aesthetics, enhancement of features, during/after sales services, personalization of deliverable

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services, after sales work sessions, *Skype* teleconferencing and recalls, reassurances such as a full or fifty percent money-back guarantee, and so forth. These are social questions that rationalize the higher price index of a company and capture the imagination of the customer as well as the quantum of a market share. The sociological question expands to include physical space and its design for the reception of consumers. The premium of an Apple show room, for example, is the welcoming attendants, the smiling ladies elegantly dressed and ready to help consumers with their queries, etc.

Beyond digital networking, is the art of developing a socially-oriented website that puts people first before economic considerations: for example, must facilitate reading of content (e.g. via landing page minimalist design, employment of bullet points to communicate ideas, reduction of clutter/spam around a page's content areas such as widgets and sidebars, clear headings and vivid subheadings, white spaces that differentiate locations of pictures, etc). By minimizing text usage, enabling users to compare specifications and contrast features that are beneficial to them, a company eases reading on its pages, and this can encourage consumers to linger on a site for longer than shorter lengths of time because they know the site is speaking not to itself but to them. In order to augment market share and trigger a sale or a conversion, a website must talk to an audience by respecting the language they understand. A website's guests should not stress on a product page but rather should enjoy attractive product images with large-font sizes educating them on the benefits of a product or service. Information about a product's gigahertz and megabytes are fine but for most guests on a website, what is critical is alignment and relevance to their lives. What is critically important is not the *device* but the social function (Southern 2014) of the device in terms of experience, excitement, pleasure, power, etc. What is critically important is the ability of a technology to address itself to the social profile of a guest segment, to support them in their search, to make content valuable and appealing, to make them feel comfortable with it. In order to realize this, customer profiles – or customer avatars – must be created for each major audience segment of your business. The more detailed these profiles are, the more useful they'll be and beneficial to one's marketing strategy.

In this way, a networking system alone is not enough; it is critical to include segmentation of the digital audience with factors such as gender, age, profession and other demographic information. A psychographic reading of the audience which incorporates their fears, desires, pains, etc, what prompts them to purchase, on what conditions they would trust one, how one can satisfy that requirement, can be legitimate ways of profiling in order to expand one's market mix. Profiling may be extended to other sociological criteria such as younger people whose children do not go to school, polygamous parents whose children are not in school, polygamous parents whose sons are in universities, children whose neighbours are married, etc. Profiling may be given a name, through the picture of an individual to match the profiling from Google Images. In this way, stock images signifying a profile may make it real, as their avatars may be spoken to in one's marketing copy, by exploiting the particular language they comprehend. By pretending that one was actually talking to these profiles as real people, one's copy would strongly appeal to consumers in real life. The social model signifies that one should stress the same customer-centered method in every component of the consumer's journey, including consumer service. Customer service is a very critical aspect of the marketing strategy because it serves to build up loyalty and to retain market share. For example, if one's website is dedicated to serving an older generation of people, it would not be appropriate to compel them to converge in a chat room for customer service rather, it would be intuitive to give a phone number to them and a person they can talk to. In this case, one has to make certain that one's website copy is large enough so that elderly people can read the inscriptions therein. In order to capture the bulk of market share, one should simply give people what they desire. On the other hand, profiles for Millennials, that is, those born from 1981 to 1996 (22-37 years old) would prefer chat-oriented systems, because of the speed and ease of use the generation is used to. Youths of this generation may not desire to use a phone, when they can type out their problems on the screen and receive an answer immediately. Comprehending such a diverse profile of consumers can be very critical for constructing the proper marketing mix.

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The Apple company does a good job of constructing and designing customer experience by creating video images in which customers unpack products and in which the video is uploaded to YouTube (Benady 2013). Unboxing by a diverse range of customers sends a social message, namely, that business with Apple is not simplistically an act of purchase in a retail store; it is also a question of consumers taking care of the bigger process: purchasing, contrasting different versions of products, product trial, reception of product, ease of installation, setting it up from opening, plugging in, turning on and functioning. In this way, purchase of Apple products is a whole range of small exciting experiences that go beyond product testing, asking of questions, into new forms of inspiration, the feeling of warm lighting in the retail store, appropriate colour outlines, store layouts, personalization of service, proximity, the look and feel of visual branding, images of clients relaxing not by discussing display dimensions and the power of processing but enjoying their iPads. Therefore, ads resonate not with consumers' pockets but with their hearts and *emotional connections*. It is about the content of narratives, videos, stories and memes with an emotional response like amusement, happiness, awe, expectation and anxiety. This is the content that goes viral because it triggers reactions in the minds of customers users' brains. Antonio Damasio's (1990) book, entitled *Descartes' Error*, reveals that people's emotions not rationality contribute critically to the decision-making process, particularly when they are purchasing products or services. Marketing strategies must start with emotion. Positive feelings impact on consumer loyalty than a trust which is more objectively evidenced. Hence, content published must be one that a target audience desires most of all.

Smart content stirs up awe or laughter, amusement and joy, through the employment of emotional language that flows naturally with emotion-trigger words. This can be effected through self- recording and play back until it sounds conversational than formalistic or stilted. Images can also be employed to evoke the same emotions. Images for content are very worthwhile because they construct visual interest on one's page replacing boring text and converting readers to subscribers. As part of the marketing mix, great images and screenshots portray the right emotional condition of the audience. Enthusiastic fanaticism for Apple's brand induces customers to desire to belong to its community of purchasers. Apple's brand messages are based on profound values, its pages, market copy and content express values, and personalities that are consistent with words employed to describe the brand, from font size to graphics and colour scheme. These are ways of showing one's clients that one's content values them as a society rather than as statistics for setting up the price. On a website, one can realize this effect by requesting open-ended questions in one's content, answering comments on one's blog posts via conversation, use of social media, referral reward programmes where consumers refer to other new customers, reach out to other consumers with email. Apple, which is an app store and retail shop, is a role model with a fan base and loyal customers who contact family and friends by word of mouth and understand the dynamism of society (Jenkins 1983).

4.3 From online market networking to cultural ethics

Beyond networking, is the empowerment of the consumer constructed via a new culture of the crowd, which has come to be referred to as *crowdculture*. In the past, businesses employed agencies and tech-artists to create brands with the hope that they would go *viral*, and new terminologies such as memes, *buzz*, *sticky* coded the branding lingua franca. However, these efforts did not yield many fruits. With the power that customers had acquired, it was no longer possible for businesses to determine how their offers would be perceived and received. Companies spent lots of money to produce content on the social media network, in the hope of constructing audiences around their products, services and brands, but consumers refused to show interest, comply and patronize. Social media networks created digital crowds that become very powerful machinery of culture that were efficient at creating activities of entertainment businesses could not produce. Crowdculture depressed organizational branding models, and engendered alternative templates of *cultural branding* in which brands cooperated with crowdcultures to defend new marketplace ideologies. Facebook and YouTube, are now the engines behind the digital cultural strategy, constructing *branded content for organizations*. Brands do well when products, and services transcode into a culture; so, the task of branding is a set of technologies devised to

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spawn cultural significance. Digital crowds innovate online culture: crowdculture shapes out which techniques are productive and which methods are counterproductive. Unlike branded content and sponsorship networking, which is a relic of the old mass media, crowdculture repackages methods that businesses borrow from online entertainment in order to celebrate their brands. Crowdculture deploys cinematic hoax, storytelling techniques, songs, and sympathetic characterizations to engage with audiences.

After the epoch of DVRs, cable networks and ads such as sponsored TV shows and events, Frito-Lay's "Frito Bandito" and Alka-Seltzer's "I Can't Believe I Ate the Whole Thing," blockbuster films for fast food chains, golf /tennis competitions and magazine contests for luxury motorcars, which companies used to celebrate their brands, the new era of crowdculture allows a flux of innovative power from the masses (e.g. artistic circles, peripheral groups, pressure/interest groups, social movement, etc) to deflect mainstream brand conventions. Social media networks cement geographically disparate groups and intensify their collaboration. Cultural communities enforce direct contacts, incubate new ideologies, initial new practices, and introduce perspectives into the art worlds, so as to break new grounds in the art of entertainment and leisure. In this globalizing trend online, subcultures are amplified through topics like liberty, new urbanism, the American Dream, bird-watching, etc. Networks of social media democratize these issues through the online click, facilitating interactions between participants offline, on the web, and radio, TV, podcasts, etc. They push for new ideas, products, services, aesthetics and modes of delivery, minimize the role of old cultural gatekeepers and with the aid of musicians, film techs, authors, designers, cartoonists, etc, they create a collaborative art world where 'scenes' are collectively constructed to repurpose ideologies. Conventional procedures of art production are reversed: one does no longer have to become a local scene member to be able to perform, one does not have to go bankrupt before producing a film. The new art world aggregates cultural entrepreneurs to refine their craftsmanship, revisit new ideas, polish their content, and generate hits through cultural prototyping, instantaneous access to trending data idea treatment in the market, the resonance of content, promotion of new talents and genres and the popularization of culture,

YouTube or Instagram celebrate success cases like PewDiePie, a Swede whose films accompanied by commentaries and video games generated 11 billion views in 2016 and 41 million subscribers. Video games conflate with the entertainment subculture in South Korea to generate a spectator sport, referred to as E-Sports, watched by 100 million people. E-Sports broadcasters give play-by-play commentaries of events in video games coupled with comedy to build an influential club. Video gamers like Ali-A, ElrubiusOMG and VanossGaming distribute content to fans who hype some of its aspects and dismiss others. As a genre crowdculture, game comedy and other genres are emerging as the new popular culture, with new topics like girls' fashion, fanboy sports, travel, sustainability and traditional foods that McDonalds', Red Bull, or Coca-Cola with its Coca-Cola Journey. By charging 'sponsored' content into audiences' feeds which are their fans, businesses like Shakira were more effective in generating brand content than Clorox or Crest. Because of structural problems of brand bureaucracy, the marketing efforts of corporations were antithetical to projects of the art worlds; they were not culturally creative or innovative. The sports and car brands, Adidas and Nike, Corona and Coors, performed to a lesser degree than celebrities and brands like Jimmy Fallon, Oprah, Bill Gates, Katy Perry, Eminem Rihanna, LeBron James, Neymar, Taylor Swift, Justin Bieber, Ellen DeGeneres, Cristiano Ronaldo, Messi, Kaká, Real Madrid and FC Barcelona took centre stage in Twitter, YouTube, Instagram, etc, to impress massive audiences as sports teams, athletes, performers, filmers, TV programmers, and video gamers dominating. Social media empowers audiences to construct rich communities around entertainers, who network directly via posts, tweets and pins. Sports businesses employ social media artists to meet with their fans in real time in the course of games, and players show photos and organize chats after they are played. Thus, the sites Apple Music SoundCloud and Vevo, find cultural value in the art world of crowdculture and cultural branding.

The Mexican food chain Chipotle benefitted enormously from the power of cultural branding from 2011 to 2013 by promoting a ground-breaking ideology that challenges *cultural orthodoxies* in conventions. It is this obsession with the unorthodox, the original as opposed to what is so obvious that constructed success for

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Chipotle which companies offering food brands like instant coffee, margarine, etc would do well to learn from. Cultural branding invests in social disruptions, alternatives, innovation and new ideologies. These ideologies may relate to issues of class, scientific food, Crowdcultures exploit these issues and push the anxieties they create into the mainstream audience vision such as concerns with high sugar foods, preservatives, GMOs, food for babies, pastured milk, organic farming, evolutionary nutrition and diets, nuclear war, the fate of the rain forests, war on drugs, urban farming, preindustrial foods and their causes. Causes are raised via animated films and then crowdculture decodes the issues into an (inter)national or a social ordeal. Film placements on social media platforms are watched by the audiences so that they generate hits, sales and profits. The films are not just entertainment, but ware mythologies that capture the ideologies of the crowdculture, the anxieties of the movement and the contentious discourses. related to an ideology. Crowdculture targets relevance, and not just trends, cultural rather than merely commodity methods, personal care issues, gender ideologies (e.g. Dove's 'Campaign for Real Beauty', Axe with its campaign 'The Axe Effect'), with the aid of photoshop images culled from fashion magazines. It targets the personal care market, generational cosmopolitanism and ideals, and sexuality aesthetics in order to gain traction in crowdcultures beyond classical segmentation models and trend strategies and tap into crowd power.

4.4 Online networking and language

Language communication is an irreplaceable UVP (unique value proposition) when it is not only simplified but also adapted to the target audience of customers. Simplification prevents the sense of overwhelming customers because a confused consumer is a lost customer. In order to minimize customer attrition, language used in sales copies and websites as a whole should be simplified and cleansed from jargon or the systematic employment of highly technical vocabularies. Direct use of language captures the consumer's attention more easily because his desires, expectations and needs are articulated intelligibly. When a retail store is designed in such a way that it takes the form of a show room, consumers are contented to pay for such a premium, because at a subtle level of the social, they know that they are being respected as people and are being given value that is beyond the worth of money. Apple ensured that consumers do not get confused by tech language and concepts, choices, options or parameters that may overwhelm them. It simplified its web and sales copy language by minimizing tech terms and avoiding jargon, and employing simple and direct words. This shows the social concern of the company for its consumers and translated into a social content marketing model that offered high tech products and services without necessarily showing off with high tech terms. This social approach took care to enlighten consumers without burdening them with too much tech information. Consumers rewarded the company with their market share loyalty. All the customer was required to do was to enjoy the brand rather than to learn it. The scannable content of its website and blog, simple schemes of colour and uncluttered, clean, blueprint, short and recollective names, lustrous features and minimal specifications of its products and services brought the company a huge success.

5.0 Conclusion

The aim of this paper was to determine whether the classical concept of online networking as an orthodoxy in the scholarship of digital marketing strategies can stand all by itself as a competitive tool capable of increasing business and organization efficiency outside the agency of literary cultural studies of the technology. This hypothesis was tested against the background of the contemporaneous context of the knowledge economy marked by companies like Apple, and it was found that networking is still relevant even in the age of shift of power from the producers to the consumers because it provides a platform for individual consumers to articulate *their* thoughts about a brand, product, ad, service, etc. However, networking in its classical configuration has to adapt to the two-way mode of communication that has replaced the single, top-down mode of dialogue with consumers. In this age of the consumer, a successful brand is not created by a 'producer' but by the *consumers* whose opinion about the employment of a product or service must be comprehended directly from their views and thoughts as articulated by them. Understanding how to leverage

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these opinions and views is a desirable way to pursue not necessarily with a view to taking power back from consumers, but with a view to rebuilding the driving engine of the contemporary political economy that would hopefully construct a better world for present and future generations of businesses. We have demonstrated that networking as a metanarrative of digital marketing strategy is too narrow a perspective from which to incorporate economic, political, social, cultural and language micro-narratives of marketing in order to optimize its cultural efficiency and literary productivity. These are critical elements of the cultural politics of discourse from which an ICT consultancy model can be constructed in the future.

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Sketch Bio

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Alfred Ndi holds a *Doctorat d'État* Degree in postcolonial digital humanities with special interests in ICT political economy and continental literature. Beyond the dialectics of *praxis/theory* in the digital marketing of race, class, ethnicity, gender, sexuality, generation, disability, nation, etc., he investigates the problematics of the hypertext in the dynamics of power/ knowledge in digital capitalism. His long term goal is to develop a critical archival database comprehensive enough to illuminate all humanities discourses for outreach educational purposes and to contribute to the foundations of global peace.

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